

Special Relativistic Considerations from $dv/dt = dv/dt \text{ partial} + \text{grad}(vv/2) + v \times \text{grad} \times v$? Part II

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It was noted in Part I that the identity, $dv/dt = dv/dt \text{ partial} + \text{grad}(vv/c) + v \times \text{grad} \times v$ ((1)) is of a similar form as the electromagnetic Lorentz force equation if one replace $vv/2$ with ϕ (electrostatic potential and $dv/dt \text{ partial}$ with $dA/dt \text{ partial}$ and $\text{grad} \times v$ with $\text{grad} \times A$.

In this note, we try to consider why these forms are so similar. We first consider the idea of a stationary object in a rest frame. We argue that when viewed from a moving frame, a rest mass becomes a possible new rest mass value and there is a Newtonian type momentum new mass $\times v$. There, however, is also a transformation of x and t because in the rest frame $x''/t'' = 0$, while in the moving $x/t = v$. We also note that v can take on any value. We suggest that this represents a linear transformation with a type of modulus which remains constant. This modulus cannot be $aa + bb = cc$ because for $x = vt$, both x and t increase indefinitely, and so suggest a $-ctct + xx$ modulus. As a result, one may obtain the Lorentz transformation. We have, however, discussed such an idea in previous notes.

The main idea of this note is to argue that the use of linear algebra and the idea of constant modulus suggest that the notion of a vector is important. In the case of two charges held at rest, there is an electrostatic energy which is like rest mass. In the moving frame there should be a new electrostatic energy and a momentum. In the rest frame, the force is $-q_2 \text{ grad } \phi''$, where q_2 is the second charge. One cannot simply use the linear transformation described above to transform grad'' and ϕ'' because instead of ϕ'' , one now has ϕ and $A = v \phi$ (momentum). The key idea, we argue, is that one must have linear partial derivatives grad and $d/dt \text{ partial}$ which act on ϕ and A combined with the vector v to create vectors (not pseudovectors). This suggests forms such as: $\text{grad } \phi$, $dA/dt \text{ partial}$, $v \cdot \text{grad } A$ and $v \times \text{grad} \times v$. Note, the last expression is a vector instead of a pseudovector on $x \rightarrow -x$ etc. We argue that this is why the identity ((1)) is of a similar form as the Lorentz force. This accounts for the similarity between ((1)) and the Lorentz force. All possible vector terms must be created in keeping with certain restrictions (e.g. $d/dt \text{ partial}$ and grad only act on ϕ , A as they do in the rest frame.)

One must, however, also preserve the idea that a force acts along a straight line between q_1 and q_2 whether the charges are moving or not. This imposes further restrictions. In fact, as shown in Part I, one can explicitly find the form of the linear transformation from vector considerations, although one would not consider these vector forms unless one assumed a linear transformation (i.e. dealt with linear algebra in the first place).

Math Identity

Even though: $dv/dt = dv/dt \text{ partial} + \text{grad}(vv/c) + v \times \text{grad} \times v$ ((1)) is a math identity, one may see that the the LHS is a vector involving a linear form of a full derivative which is linked to the two partial derivatives grad , which is a vector and $d/dt \text{ partial}$ which is not. One may write:

$$dv/dt = dv/dt \text{ partial} + v \cdot \text{grad } v \quad ((2))$$

The LHS side is a vector as is the RHS. There are, however, other vectors which may be formed using grad and v. In particular:

$$\text{Grad} (v \cdot v) \quad \text{and} \quad v \times \text{grad} \times v \quad ((3))$$

The double cross product is used because one wishes to have a vector, not a pseudovector on $x \rightarrow x$ etc. Thus, one expects ((3)) to be in the picture and they are in ((1)). In other words, if one did not know the identity ((1)), one could try to construct its pieces from purely vector considerations. We note that these vector forms may appear in other situations as will be described later in this note.

Linear Transformation

Given a particle at rest with rest mass m_0 at $x=0, t=0$, one may note that from the point of view of a frame moving with $-v$, one has x, t such that $x/t=v$. It is possible that one has $m(v)$ and certainly $m(v)v$, Newtonian momentum. One may have any value of v , and so is creating a scenario equivalent to the rest mass one. Given the linear nature of $x/t=v$ and the various equivalences, one may ask: What mathematics yields a quantity (invariant) for all of these scenarios? It seems that each scenario is linked to (x, t) and $(p, m(v))$. These appear to be vectors and linear algebra deals with linear transformations. Thus, one may expect a modulus to be an invariant. Given that from a moving frame, x grows in time as vt , one cannot use the usual $xx+tt = \text{constant}$, but $xx-cctt$ is possible. In the lab frame, one has:

$00 - cctt$ and if one has a linear transformation $x = a(v/c)v t, t = a(v/c) t$ so that $x/t=v$. Then:

$$a(v)a(v) (-1+vv/cc) cc t^2 = -cct^2 \quad \text{or} \quad a(v)=1/\sqrt{1-vv/cc} \quad ((3))$$

This also applies to $(p, m(v))$. Here c is the speed of light in a vacuum. A constant with units of speed is needed and one may independently show that c suffices.

These ideas may be extended to the potential energy of two point charges at rest a distance apart. In such a case:

$Q \phi = \text{electrostatic energy in the rest frame which should transform to:}$

$$\phi, \quad v \phi = A = \text{momentum} \quad ((4))$$

Given that force is $-\text{grad} \phi$ in the rest frame, one may ask: Can one simply transform ϕ and $\text{grad} \phi$ using the linear transformation above? We suggest the answer is no.

The linear transformation is associated with vector and ϕ is a scalar which becomes ϕ and $v \phi = A$ a vector. $\text{Grad} \phi$ is a vector so one expects a vector as seen in the moving frame, but with d/dt partial and grad acting on ϕ and A . The velocity vector may also be used, but it is not acted on by d/dt partial or ϕ . (We make this assumption.)

The Importance of Vectors in the Moving Charge Scenario

We suggest that one cannot simply transform grad" and phi" from the rest frame. Rather, one must consider (like in the identity ((1))) all possible vector forms of phi and A with the linear operator d/dt partial and grad acting on phi and A together with the velocity vector which is not acted upon by d/dt partial or grad.. Given that force = -q grad" phi" in the rest frame, we assume that the linear d/dt partial and grad operators must act on either A or phi, but not on v by itself. No pseudovectors are allowed.

In such a case, one has:

$$\text{Grad } \phi, \quad \frac{dA}{dt} \text{ partial}, \quad v \cdot \text{grad } A \text{ and } v \times \text{grad } \times A. \quad ((4a))$$

Again, the last term includes double x because one wants a vector, not pseudovector under $x \rightarrow -x$ etc. Given that the pseudovector contains two factors of v, we also consider $v \cdot \text{grad } A$ with two factors of v.

We argue, however, that the notion of electric field (i.e. force between charges along a line between the two) must still exist as seen from the moving frame. We argue that this is an important constraint which actually yields the Lorentz factor $1/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$ as noted in Part I.

We see that grad phi and $\frac{dA}{dt}$ partial yield an x-component, while $v \times \text{grad } \times A$ does not. Further, we note that one may always choose v to be in the x-direction and then:

$$v \cdot \text{grad } A = vv \frac{d}{dx} \phi \quad ((4b))$$

$\frac{d}{dx} \phi$, however, is already accounted for by grad phi and so one need not worry about $v \cdot \text{grad } A$. We consider later the Lorentz transformation which is needed in order to make grad phi, $\frac{dA}{dt}$ partial proportional to the vector (x,y,z). If one includes ((4b)), the vector (x,y,z) requirement remains and so this term $v \cdot \text{grad } A$ contributes no independent information.

In the rest frame, Force = -q grad" phi". We suggest that in the moving frame, an electric field must be created from: grad phi and $\frac{dA}{dt}$ partial and must be a vector lying along the vector (x,y,z) which joins the two charges.

$$g(v) \text{Phi}"(x",y",x") = \phi(x,y,z) \quad \text{where } y"=y, z"=z \text{ and } x" = x-vt \quad ((5))$$

and $x" = g(v)(x-vt)$ as well as $\phi = g(v) \phi."$ (x",y",z) One may then rewrite x",y",z" in terms of x,t. Then:

$$-\text{grad } \phi - \frac{dA}{dt} \text{ partial yields } g(v) (1-vv/cc) g(v)g(v) \frac{d}{dx} \phi \text{ for the x-component } ((6))$$

The double factor of $g(v)g(v)$ appears because phi" is a function of $r=\sqrt{x"x"+y"y"+z"z"}/$

Note: $A = v \phi$ lies in the x direction here (vector). $d/dt \text{ partial} \rightarrow -v d/dx \text{ partial}$

If one assumes only a Galilean transformation $x'' = x - vt$, then one does not obtain a vector (x, y, z) as noted in Part I. Thus, vector considerations are enough to determine the Lorentz factor $1/\sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}$, although one would not arrive at this conclusion unless one assumed a linear transformation in the first place, we argue.

We next examine the two terms $v \cdot \text{grad} A$ and $v \times \text{grad} \times v$. The second term has no x component for $A = \phi v$ (in the x direction).

$v \times \text{grad} \times A$ is the usual $v \times B$ term of electromagnetism.

We have already dropped $v \cdot \text{grad} A$.

Out of curiosity, we note that if one constructs vector terms using only $d/dt \text{ partial}$, grad and v (vector), one obtains dv/dt from ((1)). This expression is actually part of $F = dp/dt = qE + q v \times B$.

We have excluded $A \times \text{grad} \times A$ terms, for example, because we argued above that $d/dt \text{ partial}$ or grad must act on A or ϕ because they do so in the rest frame. Thus, force is physically related to the dropping off (derivatives) of ϕ with r .

Generalization to Two Different Velocities

In the above section, we considered the rest case of two fixed charges and so both have the same velocity as seen from the moving frame. What if one has a source charge moving with v_1 (vector) and a test charge moving with v_2 ? In such a case, $v \times \text{grad} \times A$ could be generalized to:

$$v_2 \times (\text{grad} \times A(v_1)) \quad ((7))$$

What about $v \cdot \text{grad} A$? This would need to be generalized as well to: $v_2 \cdot \text{grad} A$. This, however, suggests that the electric field of the moving particle does not lie along a vector joining the two charges. We already rejected $v \cdot \text{grad} A$ as bringing in no independent information. If one insists on an electric field along a line joining the two charges, then it seems that one may drop $v_2 \cdot \text{grad} A(v_1)$. Thus, v_2 is only sensitive to $\text{grad} \times A(v_1)$, i.e. the magnetic field.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we note that one may consider a linear transformation of a rest mass m_0 at $x'' = 0$ at t'' to $m(v)$, $m(v)v$ (momentum), x , t such that $x/t = v$. We stress a linear transformation which seems to be in keeping with $v = x/t$. We note that one may have any v (any moving frame) and that all are equivalent to the m_0 rest frame one. This suggests many vectors, but all having something in common, i.e. a constant or invariant modulus. This, however, cannot be the usual

$xx+tt$ because x grows indefinitely with time as seen in the moving frame. Thus, $xx-cctt$ may be used. As a result, one may obtain a Lorentz transformation.

We argue, however, that this analysis is not enough. We note that if one has two charges (both positive for example) there is an electrostatic energy $q\phi$ which is like m_0 and transforms to ϕ , $A=v\phi$ (vector). In the rest frame, Force = q Electric field = $-q \text{ grad } \phi$. One cannot simply transform grad and ϕ , we argue, because the momentum piece A contains ϕ and should create force. Thus, we suggest that vector analysis is required.

We note identity ((1)) for which all possible vector (not pseudovector) pieces are created using v , d/dt partial and grad . Thus, even though ((1)) is an identity, its separate pieces may be obtained through vector considerations,

We suggest that the same vector analysis applies to the case of $-\text{grad } \phi$ in the rest frame. In the moving frame, one has d/dt partial, grad , v , ϕ and A . We suggest that d/dt partial and grad must act on either ϕ or A (but not v) because they do so in the rest frame. This is the physical essence of the force. One may then create vector (not pseudovector) contributions such as: dA/dt partial, $\text{grad } \phi$, $v \cdot \text{grad } A$ and $v \times \text{grad } \times A$. We argue that $v \cdot \text{grad } A$ brings in no new information and eliminate it. We then argue that $v \times \text{grad } \times A$ has no x -component and may be generalized to v describing a v^2 of a test charge. Thus, we argue that dA/dt partial and $\text{grad } \phi$ must combine to create an electric field (proportional to force) in the moving case, which lies along the vector (x,y,z) . As argued in Part I, this vector consideration is enough to derive the Lorentz factor $1/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$, although the assumption of a linear transformation is critical for this line of reasoning.

Thus, we suggest that creating vector terms accounts for the similarity of the math identity ((1)) and the Lorentz force equation.